

Molecular Characterisation of Virulence Factors in *Cryptococcus* spp. Isolated from Humans, Pigeons, and *Eucalyptus* Sources

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Abstract

This study aimed to isolate and identify *Cryptococcus* species from three distinct sources: sputum samples of pigeon fanciers, dried pigeon droppings, and eucalyptus tree leaves. A total of 150 specimens were collected over a two-month period, comprising 50 samples each from human sputum, pigeon droppings collected across various areas of Baghdad, and eucalyptus leaves obtained from the Baghdad College of Veterinary Medicine. All samples were cultured on Sabouraud dextrose agar supplemented with chloramphenicol and incubated at 25°C for 2–3 days.

From the initial cultures, 20 isolates presumptively identified as *Cryptococcus* spp. were obtained: 6 isolates (12%) from human sputum, 9 isolates (18%) from pigeon droppings, and 5 isolates (10%) from eucalyptus leaves, giving an overall recovery rate of 13.3%. Molecular identification using PCR was employed to detect two key virulence genes: *CAP64* (associated with capsule formation) and *LAC1* (involved in melanin production). These genes were detected in 13 out of 14 confirmed *Cryptococcus* isolates (92.85%). Specifically, 75% of *C. neoformans* isolates from human samples carried these genes, while the *C. albidus* isolate lacked them. All *Cryptococcus* isolates from pigeon droppings and eucalyptus leaves tested positive for both virulence genes (100%).

Keywords: *Cryptococcus* spp., virulence genes, *CAP64*, *LAC1*, pigeon droppings, eucalyptus leaves.

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Introduction

Opportunistic yeasts and filamentous fungi are responsible for three primary forms of mycotic infections: (1) superficial and cutaneous, (2) subcutaneous, and (3) systemic or deep mycoses (Rathore, et al., 2022; Zhao, et al., 2023; Kamal, & Al-Hadad, 2023; Mohammed, & Kamal, 2025). Numerous cases of cryptococcosis, candidiasis, and aspergillosis have been documented across the Americas, Europe, and Africa, confirming their global occurrence (De Hoog, et al., 2005; Jassem, et al., 2013; Mahmood, 2015). Since the 1980s, the increasing number of individuals with weakened immune systems has made opportunistic fungal infections a significant public health challenge (Francisco, de Jong, & Hagen, 2021;

Mukaremera, 2023; Mohammed, & Al-Gburi, 2023; Khalaf, & Rejah, 2024). The mortality rates associated with the three leading invasive fungal pathogens—*Aspergillus*, *Candida*, and *Cryptococcus*—range from 10% to as high as 90% (Steinbach, & Stevens, 2003; Filioti, Spiroglou, & Roilides, 2007; Longley, et al., 2008; Park, et al., 2009; Kadim, et al., 2019).

Cryptococcus, a fungal pathogen, causes cryptococcosis, particularly among immunocompromised individuals. The two main species implicated in human disease are *Cryptococcus neoformans* and *Cryptococcus gattii* (Morales-López, & Garcia-Effron, 2021; Black, et al., 2024). These organisms are found in various environmental reservoirs worldwide, with typical exposure occurring through contact with soil or avian droppings (Lin, Shiau, & Fang, 2015; Refai, El-Hariri, & Alarousy, 2017). Morphologically, these pathogens resemble encapsulated yeasts and are capable of causing serious infections (Diniz-Lima, et al., 2022; Ristow, et al., 2023; Khalaf, & Rejah, 2024). Individuals with underlying conditions such as AIDS, diabetes, chronic hepatic or renal illnesses, prolonged corticosteroid use, or those who have undergone organ transplantation are especially at risk (Diniz-Lima, et al., 2022; Kamal, & Al-haddad, 2022).

Virulence factors are broadly defined as components or characteristics of a pathogen that contribute to host damage (Chen, et al., 2022; Montoya, Magwene, & Perfect, 2021; Denham, et al., 2022). *C. neoformans* is known to produce a variety of virulence-associated enzymes, including proteases and lipases—similar to those produced by other microbial pathogens such as bacteria and fungi (Ghanem, & Sivasubramanian, 2021; Alegre-González, et al., 2021; Poplin, et al., 2024). Additionally, this species secretes urease, an enzyme involved in nitrogen metabolism by catalysing the breakdown of urea into CO₂ and ammonia. This enzyme plays a critical role in pathogenesis and is used as a diagnostic indicator for cryptococcosis (Rizzo, et al., 2021; Yu, et al., 2021; Yang, et al., 2022; Mohammed, & Kamal, 2025).

Among the most studied virulence factors in *C. neoformans* are its polysaccharide capsule and melanin pigment. These two components are not only vital for the pathogen's virulence but also provide protection against host immune responses (Baddley, et al., 2021; Wang, et al., 2022; Huang, et al., 2024).

Methodology

LAC1 Gene Primers

Table 1. LAC1 Gene Primers Used in the Study of *Cryptococcus* spp.

Primer	Sequence	Primer sequence	Tm (°C)	GC%	Size of Product (bp)	
<i>LAC1</i> <i>C. neoformans</i>	F	5'- AGAAGGGAAGGAAGGTGATG -3'	60.3	50 %	480bp	Musavinasab-Mobarakeh, Shams-Ghahfarokhi, & Razzaghi-Abyaneh, (2021)
	R	5' TATACCTCACAACCGCCAAT -3'	57.8	41 %		
<i>LAC1</i> <i>C. gattii</i>	F	5'- AACATGTTCCCTGGGCCTGTG -3'	60.3	50 %	469bp	
	R	5' ATGAGAATTGAATCGCCTTGT -3'	57.8	41 %		
<i>LAC1</i> <i>C. albidus</i>	F	5'- AGAAGGGAAGGAAGGTGATG -3'	60.3	50 %	480bp	
	R	5' TATACCTCACAACCGCCAAT -3'	57.8	41 %		

CAP64 Gene Primers

Table 2. CAP64 Gene Primers Used in the Study of *Cryptococcus* spp.

Primer	Sequence	Primer sequence	Tm (°C)	GC%	Size of Product (bp)	
<i>CAP64</i> <i>C. neoformans</i>	F	5'- CTCTACGTCGAGCAAGTCAAG -3'	60.3	50 %	559bp	Imanishi-Shimizu,
	R	5' TCCGCTGCACAAGTGATACCC -3'	57.8	41 %		

<i>CAP64</i> <i>C. gattii</i>	F	5'- CTGATCACACCGATCTCGTCATTCT - 3'	60.3	50 %	833bp	et al. (2021)
	R	5' GATCAGGCCTCACAAGGAT -3'	57.8	41 %		
<i>CAP64</i> <i>C. albidus</i>	F	5'- CTCTACGTCGAGCAAAGTCAAAG -3'	60.3	50 %	559bp	
	R	5' TCCGCTGCACAAGTGATACCC -3'	57.8	41 %		

Preparation of Culture Media

Sabouraud Dextrose Agar (SDA):

To prepare the medium, 65 grams of SDA powder were dissolved in one litre of distilled water. Chloramphenicol was added at a concentration of 0.05 g/mL to inhibit bacterial contamination. The mixture was stirred continuously while heating and sterilised in an autoclave at 121°C and 15 psi for 15 minutes. After cooling to approximately 50°C, the sterile medium was poured into petri dishes and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours before storage at 4°C.

Samples Collection

Human Sputum Samples:

Sputum samples were obtained from pigeon breeders of different age groups. The samples were transported aseptically to the Mycology Laboratory of the Zoonotic Disease Research Unit. Each sample was streaked onto SDA supplemented with chloramphenicol (Staib, et al., 1987). Suspected yeast colonies were stained with India ink and lactophenol cotton blue, followed by a urease test. Further identification was confirmed using specific media.

Pigeon Droppings:

Fifty samples of pigeon droppings were collected from various pigeon shelters and placed in sterile plastic bags. Approximately 20–30 grams of each sample were weighed and diluted in saline (0.9%) containing 200 mg/L chloramphenicol to achieve a 1:10 dilution. The mixture was shaken for 30 minutes and left to settle. From the supernatant, 0.5 mL aliquots were streaked onto SDA. Confirmation involved staining (India ink, lactophenol cotton blue), urease testing, and growth on BSA and CDA media (Zarrin, Met al., 2010).

Eucalyptus Leaves:

Fifty eucalyptus leaf samples were collected from locations in Baghdad and placed in sterile plastic bags. Samples were transported on ice to the Zoonotic Diseases Unit, College of Veterinary Medicine. Two grams of leaves were rinsed in sterile water and then immersed in 20 mL of sterile saline with 10 mg/mL chloramphenicol. The mixture was homogenised for four minutes, then left at room temperature for 30 minutes. A loopful of the supernatant was streaked onto SDA plates, which were incubated at 30°C for 48 hours (Elhariri, et al., 2016).

Results and Discussion

Colonies suspected to be *Cryptococcus* species were observed on Sabouraud Dextrose Agar (SDA). These isolates displayed a creamy texture, convex elevation, and a glistening appearance, often exhibiting a pale off-white to beige hue. After incubation at 25°C and 30°C for 2–3 days, the mucoid appearance of the colonies became evident, which is attributed to the production of a polysaccharide capsule, as illustrated in Figure 1.

These observations are consistent with earlier reports by Washington, et al. (2024) and Khanal, Sharma, & Deb (2002), who noted that mucoid colonies are often the first indicator of *Cryptococcus* presence. The

colonies are typically fast-growing, soft, glistening, mucoid or creamy in appearance, smooth, convex, and slightly pink, tan, or yellowish-brown on solid media—a finding further supported by Washington, et al. (2024); Okagaki, et al. (2010) and Firacative, Trilles, & Meyer (2021). Isolates from various sources (human, pigeon droppings, and eucalyptus leaves) shared morphological traits: spherical, encapsulated, and non-myceliated cells. Notably, *C. neoformans* is characterised by a distinct mucinous capsule, especially when incubated at 30°C, which also supports compact basidiospore formation as noted by Karkowska-Kuleta, Rapala-Kozik, & Kozik (2009) and Wang, et al. (2024).

Figure 1. Suspected *Cryptococcus* spp. Appeared within 2-3 Days of Incubation in 25°C on SDA

Table 3. Primary Isolation of *Cryptococcus* sp. from Human and Natural Habitat

Sources of sample	No. of samples	Primary isolation in lab	
		No. of +ve	%
Human	50	6	12
Droppings	50	9	18
Eucalyptus leaves	50	5	10
Total	150	20	13.3

Table 4. Positive Results of Suspected *Cryptococcus* spp. Isolates in Stains, Selective Differential Media and Biochemical Test

Sources of sample	Stains		Selective differential media						Biochemical test
	LPCB	INDIA INK	BSA	CDA	BHIA with cycloheximide	BHIA with methyl dopa	EA	ELA	Urease test
Human (6)	6 +ve	3 +ve	3 +ve	4 +ve	–	6 +ve	5 +ve	6 +ve	6 +ve
Droppings (9)	9 +ve	6 +ve	6 +ve	6 +ve	–	9 +ve	9 +ve	9 +ve	4 +ve
Eucalyptus leaves (5)	5 +ve	–	–	5 +ve	–	5 +ve	5 +ve	5 +ve	4 +ve

Molecular Detection of Virulence Factors in *Cryptococcus* spp.

Out of 14 suspected *Cryptococcus* spp. isolates—four from humans, six from pigeon droppings, and four from eucalyptus leaves—a conventional PCR assay was conducted to confirm molecular identity and detect two key virulence genes: **CAP64** (responsible for capsule formation) and **LAC1** (involved in melanin production).

Table 5. Virulence gene in *Cryptococcus* spp.

Sources of sample	Spp. and NO. of positive isolates	Gene			
		<i>CAP64</i>		<i>LAC1</i>	
		NO.	%	NO.	%
Human sputum	<i>C. neoformans</i> (3)	3	100	3	100
	<i>C. albidus</i> (1)	0	0	0	0
Pigeon dropping	<i>C. neoformans</i> (6)	6	100	6	100
Eucalyptus leaves	<i>C. gattii</i> (4)	4	100	4	100
Total	14	13	92.85	13	92.85

Figure 2. Gel Electrophoresis for PCR Product of *LAC1* Gene, (Agarose 2%, at 70 volts, 60min.), M: DNA ladder (10000-100bp). Visualized under U.V light after Staining with Red Safe, (1-6) Represent *C. neoformans* from Pigeon Dropping, (7-9) *C. neoformans* from Human Sputum, *C. albidus* (14) from Human Sputum was Lack this Gene have Product size 469bp, (10-13) *C. gattii* from Eucalyptus Leaves with Size of Product 480bp

PCR results revealed the presence of both **CAP64** and **LAC1** genes in 13 out of the 14 isolates, with *C. albidus* being the only isolate lacking both genes (Table 5). These findings corroborate previous studies (Ito-Kuwa, et al., 2007; Rodrigues, et al., 2015), which documented the detection of the capsule-encoding CAP64 gene and the LAC1 gene responsible for melanin synthesis in *C. neoformans* and *C. gattii* isolates from similar environmental and clinical sources (Meyer, et al., 2009; Specht, et al., 2024; Khalaf, & Rejah, 2024).

The **LAC1** gene, which governs melanin pigment production—a known virulence factor—was detected in all *C. neoformans* and *C. gattii* isolates but absent in *C. albidus*, as also reported by Kassi, et al. (2016); Samarasinghe, et al. (2018) and Wang, et al. (2022). PCR assays identified LAC1 at 469 bp in *C. neoformans* and 480 bp in *C. gattii*, which aligns with the findings of Ito-Kuwa, et al. (2007) and Kadim, et al. (2019).

Figure 3. Gel Electrophoresis for PCR Product of (CAP64), (Agarose 2%, at 70 volts, 60min.), M: DNA Ladder (10000-100bp). Visualized under U.V Light after Staining with Red Safe, (1-6) Represent *C. neoformans* from Pigeon Dropping, (7-9) *C. neoformans* from Human Sputum, *C. albidus* (14) from Human Sputum was Lack this Gene have Product Size 833bp, (10-13) *C. gattii* from Eucalyptus Leaves Size of Product 559bp.

Similarly, the CAP64 gene, integral to the formation of the polysaccharide capsule and directly associated with the pathogenicity of *Cryptococcus* spp., was present in all *C. neoformans* and *C. gattii* isolates but absent in *C. albidus* (Figure 3). These findings are supported by Wilder, et al. (2002); Okabayashi, Hasegawa, & Watanabe (2007) and Imanishi-Shimizu, et al. (2021), who highlighted the role of CAP64 in virulence. However, these results contrast with those of Okabayashi, et al. (2005), who reported the lack of CAP64 gene expression in some *C. neoformans* isolates. PCR amplification of CAP64 showed band sizes of 833 bp in *C. neoformans* and 559 bp in *C. gattii*, while *C. albidus* exhibited no amplification.

Conclusions

CAP64 and LAC1 virulence genes were detected in all clinical and environmental isolates of *C. neoformans* and *C. gattii* using conventional PCR, confirming their pathogenic potential. In contrast, *C. albidus* lacked both genes, suggesting a lower virulence profile.

Phylogenetic analysis demonstrated a 99% genetic similarity between the studied isolates of *C. neoformans* and *C. gattii* and their respective reference strains. *C. albidus* also showed a perfect match with known reference sequences, indicating accurate species identification.

Reference

- Alegre-González, D., Herrera, S., Bernal, J., Soriano, A., & Bodro, M. (2021). Disseminated *Cryptococcus neoformans* infection associated to COVID-19. *Medical Mycology Case Reports*, 34, 35–37. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mmcr.2021.10.001>
- Baddley, J. W., Chen, S. C., Huisin, C., Benedict, K., DeBess, E. E., Galanis, E., Chiller, T. M., & Pappas, P. G. (2021). MSG07: An international cohort study comparing epidemiology and outcomes of patients with *Cryptococcus neoformans* or *Cryptococcus gattii* infections. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*, 73(7), 1133–1141. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cid/ciab374>
- Black, B., da Silva, L. B. R., Hu, G., Qu, X., Smith, D. F., Magaña, A. A., & Kronstad, J. W. (2024). Glutathione-mediated redox regulation in *Cryptococcus neoformans* impacts virulence. *Nature Microbiology*, 9(8), 2084–2098. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41564-024-01573-5>
- Chen, Y., Shi, Z. W., Strickland, A. B., & Shi, M. (2022). *Cryptococcus neoformans* infection in the central nervous system: The battle between host and pathogen. *Journal of Fungi*, 8(10), 1069. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jof8101069>
- De Hoog, G. S., Guarro, J., Gené, J., & Figueras, M. J. (2005). *Atlas of clinical fungi* (2nd ed.). Centraalbureau voor Schimmelcultures.
- Denham, S. T., Brammer, B., Chung, K. Y., Wambaugh, M. A., Bednarek, J. M., Guo, L., Daugherty, S., Lin, X., & Brown, J. C. (2022). A dissemination-prone morphotype enhances extrapulmonary organ entry by *Cryptococcus neoformans*. *Cell Host & Microbe*, 30(10), 1382–1400.e7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chom.2022.08.008>
- Diniz-Lima, I., Fonseca, L. M. D., Silva-Junior, E. B. D., Guimarães-de-Oliveira, J. C., Freire-de-Lima, L., Nascimento, D. O., Morrot, A., Previato, J. O., Mendonça-Previato, L., Decote-Ricardo, D., & Freire-de-Lima, C. G. (2022). *Cryptococcus*: History, epidemiology and immune evasion. *Applied Sciences*, 12(14), 7086. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app12147086>
- Elhariri, M., Hamza, D., Elhelw, R., & Refai, M. (2016). Eucalyptus tree: A potential source of *Cryptococcus neoformans* in Egyptian environment. *International Journal of Microbiology*, 2016, 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2016/4080723>

- Filioti, J., Spiroglou, K., & Roilides, E. (2007). Invasive candidiasis in pediatric intensive care patients: Epidemiology, risk factors, management, and outcome. *Intensive Care Medicine*, 33(7), 1272–1283. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00134-007-0644-6>
- Firacative, C., Trilles, L., & Meyer, W. (2021). Recent advances in *Cryptococcus* and cryptococcosis. *Microorganisms*, 10(1), 13. <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms10010013>
- Francisco, E. C., de Jong, A. W., & Hagen, F. (2021). Cryptococcosis and *Cryptococcus*. *Mycopathologia*, 186(5), 729–731. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11046-021-00583-3>
- Ghanem, H., & Sivasubramanian, G. (2021). *Cryptococcus neoformans* meningoencephalitis in an immunocompetent patient after COVID-19 infection. *Case Reports in Infectious Diseases*, 2021, 5597473. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/5597473>
- Huang, J., Larmore, C. J., Priest, S. J., Xu, Z., Dietrich, F. S., Yadav, V., Wang, Y., Wang, P., & Heitman, J. (2024). Distinct evolutionary trajectories following loss of RNA interference in *Cryptococcus neoformans*. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 121(47), e2416656121. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2416656121>
- Imanishi-Shimizu, Y., Kamogawa, Y., Shimada, Y., & Shimizu, K. (2021). A capsule-associated gene of *Cryptococcus neoformans*, CAP64, is involved in pH homeostasis. *Microbiology*, 167(6). <https://doi.org/10.1099/mic.0.001048>
- Ito-Kuwa, S., Nakamura, K., Aoki, S., & Vidotto, V. (2007). Serotype identification of *Cryptococcus neoformans* by multiplex PCR. *Mycoses*, 50(4), 277–281. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1439-0507.2007.01352.x>
- Jassem, I. K., Mohammed, S. J., Tawfeq, T. W., & Karhoot, J. M. (2013). *Cryptococcus neoformans* isolated from burn patients in Burn Hospital in Baghdad. *Journal of the Faculty of Medicine Baghdad*, 55(4), 362–364. <https://doi.org/10.32007/jfacmedbagdad.554586>
- Kadim, N. H., Rejah, B. K., Mahdi, R. T., & Khalaf, A. M. (2019, February). Radium and uranium concentration in some plants in Iraq. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (Vol. 1178, No. 1, p. 012022). IOP Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1178/1/012022>
- Kamal, I. M., & Al-Hadad, Z. A. (2023). Isolation and molecular identification of pathogenic *Cryptococcus gattii* from natural habitat. *Eastern Journal of Agricultural and Biological Sciences*, 3(1), 30–38.
- Kamal, I. M., & Al-haddad, Z. A. A. (2022). Isolation and molecular identification of pathogenic *Cryptococcus neoformans* from pigeon dropping and human sputum. *International Journal of Health Sciences*, 6(S4), 8363–8374. <https://doi.org/10.53730/ijhs.v6nS4.10554>
- Karkowska-Kuleta, J., Rapala-Kozik, M., & Kozik, A. (2009). Fungi pathogenic to humans: Molecular bases of virulence of *Candida albicans*, *Cryptococcus neoformans* and *Aspergillus fumigatus*. *Acta Biochimica Polonica*, 56(2), 211–224. https://doi.org/10.18388/abp.2009_3416
- Kassi, F. K., Drakulovski, P., Bellet, V., Krasteva, D., Gatchitch, F., Doumbia, A., Koné, M., Kone, A., Coulibaly, D., & Bertout, S. (2016). Molecular epidemiology reveals genetic diversity among 363 isolates of the *Cryptococcus neoformans* and *Cryptococcus gattii* species complex in 61 Ivorian HIV-positive patients. *Mycoses*, 59(12), 811–817. <https://doi.org/10.1111/myc.12542>
- Khalaf, A. M., & Rejah, B. K. (2024). Study the quality of IMRT and VMAT treatment planning techniques (TPS) using indices of achievement (IOA) nasopharyngeal cancer plans. *Ibn AL-Haitham Journal for Pure and Applied Sciences*, 37(1), 128–139. <https://doi.org/10.30526/37.1.3277>
- Khalaf, A. M., & Rejah, B. K. (2024). Study the quality of nasopharyngeal plans using evaluation indexes of IMRT and VMAT treatment planning techniques. *Baghdad Science Journal*, 21(2), 0437.

- Khanal, B., Sharma, S. K., & Deb, M. (2002). Cryptococcal meningitis in a non-AIDS patient. *Journal of Nepal Medical Association*, 41, 323–325.
- Lin, Y. Y., Shiau, S., & Fang, C. T. (2015). Risk factors for invasive *Cryptococcus neoformans* diseases: A case-control study. *PLOS ONE*, 10(3), e0119090. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0119090>
- Longley, N., Muzoora, C., Taseera, K., Mwesigye, J., Rwebembera, J., Chakera, A., Wall, E., Andia, I., Jaffar, S., & Harrison, T. S. (2008). Dose response effect of high-dose fluconazole for HIV-associated cryptococcal meningitis in southwestern Uganda. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*, 47(12), 1556–1561. <https://doi.org/10.1086/593194>
- Mahmood, F. A. (2015). Isolation and identification of *Cryptococcus neoformans* from human skin lesions and application of animal experiment (in vivo). *The Iraqi Journal of Veterinary Medicine*, 39(1), 85–89.
- Meyer, W., Aanensen, D. M., Boekhout, T., Cogliati, M., Diaz, M. R., Esposto, M. C., Fisher, M., Gilgado, F., Hagen, F., Kaocharoen, S., Litvintseva, A. P., Mitchell, T. G., Simwami, S. P., Trilles, L., Viviani, M. A., & Kwon-Chung, J. (2009). Consensus multi-locus sequence typing scheme for *Cryptococcus neoformans* and *Cryptococcus gattii*. *Medical Mycology*, 47(6), 561–570. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13693780902953886>
- Mohammed, H. F., & Al-Gburi, N. M. (2023). Antimicrobial resistance and biofilm formation of *Enterococcus* spp. isolated from human and pet animals. *Eastern Journal of Agricultural and Biological Sciences*, 3(1), 39–49.
- Mohammed, H. F., & Kamal, I. M. (2025). Review of multidrug sensitivity and resistance in *Enterococcus*.
- Montoya, M. C., Magwene, P. M., & Perfect, J. R. (2021). Associations between *Cryptococcus* genotypes, phenotypes, and clinical parameters of human disease: A review. *Journal of Fungi*, 7(4), 260. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jof7040260>
- Morales-López, S. E., & Garcia-Effron, G. (2021). Infections due to rare *Cryptococcus* species: A literature review. *Journal of Fungi*, 7(4), 279. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jof7040279>
- Mukaremera, L. (2023). The *Cryptococcus* wall: A different wall for a unique lifestyle. *PLoS Pathogens*, 19(2), e1011141. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.ppat.1011141>
- Musavinasab-Mobarakeh, S. A., Shams-Ghahfarokhi, M., & Razzaghi-Abyaneh, M. (2021). Effect of *Allium cepa* on LAC1 gene expression and physiological activities in *Cryptococcus neoformans*. *Current Medical Mycology*, 7(1), 38–43. <https://doi.org/10.18502/cmm.7.1.6297>
- Okabayashi, K., Hasegawa, A., & Watanabe, T. (2007). Microreview: Capsule-associated genes of *Cryptococcus neoformans*. *Mycopathologia*, 163(1), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11046-006-0080-7>
- Okabayashi, K., Kano, R., Watanabe, S., & Hasegawa, A. (2005). Expression of capsule-associated genes of *Cryptococcus neoformans*. *Mycopathologia*, 160(1), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11046-005-0001-1>
- Okagaki, L. H., Strain, A. K., Nielsen, J. N., Charlier, C., Baltés, N. J., Chrétien, F., Heitman, J., Dromer, F., & Nielsen, K. (2010). Cryptococcal cell morphology affects host cell interactions and pathogenicity. *PLoS Pathogens*, 6(6), e1000953. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.ppat.1000953>
- Park, B. J., Wannemuehler, K. A., Marston, B. J., Govender, N., Pappas, P. G., & Chiller, T. M. (2009). Estimation of the current global burden of cryptococcal meningitis among persons living with HIV/AIDS. *AIDS*, 23(4), 525–530. <https://doi.org/10.1097/QAD.0b013e328322ffac>
- Poplin, V., Smith, C., Caceres, D. H., Herkert, P. F., Jegede, O., Thompson, G. R., & Bahr, N. C. (2024). Geographical distribution of the *Cryptococcus gattii* species complex: A systematic review. *The Lancet Microbe*, 5(1), e14–e23. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2666-5247\(24\)00161-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2666-5247(24)00161-7)

- Rathore, S. S., Sathiyamoorthy, J., Lalitha, C., & Ramakrishnan, J. (2022). A holistic review on *Cryptococcus neoformans*. *Microbial Pathogenesis*, *166*, 105521. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micpath.2022.105521>
- Refai, M., El-Hariri, M., & Alarousy, R. (2017). Cryptococcosis in animals and birds: A review. *European Journal of Academic Essays*, *4*(8), 202–223.
- Ristow, L. C., Jezewski, A. J., Chadwick, B. J., Stamnes, M. A., Lin, X., & Krysan, D. J. (2023). *Cryptococcus neoformans* adapts to the host environment through TOR-mediated remodeling of phospholipid asymmetry. *Nature Communications*, *14*, 6587. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-42318-y>
- Rizzo, J., Wong, S. S. W., Gazi, A. D., Moyrand, F., Chaze, T., Commere, P. H., Novault, S., Matondo, M., Péhau-Arnaudet, G., Reis, F. C. G., Vos, M., Alves, L. R., May, R. C., Nimrichter, L., Rodrigues, M. L., Aimaniana, V., & Janbon, G. (2021). *Cryptococcus* extracellular vesicles properties and their use as vaccine platforms. *Journal of Extracellular Vesicles*, *10*(10), e12129. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jev2.12129>
- Rodrigues, J., Fonseca, F. L., Schneider, R. O., Godinho, R. M. D. C., Firacative, C., Maszewska, K., Trilles, L., Cordero, R. J. B., Zaragoza, O., & Rodrigues, M. L. (2015). Pathogenic diversity amongst serotype C VGIII and VGIV *Cryptococcus gattii* isolates. *Scientific Reports*, *5*, 11226. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep11226>
- Samarasinghe, H., Aceituno-Caicedo, D., Cogliati, M., Kwon-Chung, K. J., Rickerts, V., Velegaki, A., Ackaglar, S., & Xu, J. (2018). Genetic factors and genotype-environment interactions contribute to variation in melanin production in the fungal pathogen *Cryptococcus neoformans*. *Scientific Reports*, *8*, 9824. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-27813-3>
- Specht, C. A., Wang, R., Oliveira, L. V. N., Hester, M. M., Gomez, C., Mou, Z., Carlson, D., Lee, C. K., Hole, C. R., Lam, W. C., Upadhy, R., Lodge, J. K., & Levitz, S. M. (2024). Immunological correlates of protection mediated by a whole organism, *Cryptococcus neoformans*, vaccine deficient in chitosan. *mBio*, *15*(8), e01746-24. <https://doi.org/10.1128/mbio.01746-24>
- Staib, F., Seibold, M., Antweiler, E., Fröhlich, B., Weber, S., & Blisse, A. (1987). The brown colour effect (BCE) of *Cryptococcus neoformans* in the diagnosis, control and epidemiology of *C. neoformans* infections in AIDS patients. *Zentralblatt für Bakteriologie, Mikrobiologie und Hygiene. Series A: Medical Microbiology, Infectious Diseases, Virology, Parasitology*, *266*(1–2), 167–177. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0176-6724\(87\)80018-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0176-6724(87)80018-3)
- Steinbach, W. J., & Stevens, D. A. (2003). Review of newer antifungal and immunomodulatory strategies for invasive aspergillosis. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*, *37*(Supplement_3), S157–S187. <https://doi.org/10.1086/376525>
- Wang, K., Espinosa, V., Wang, Y., Lemenze, A., Kumamoto, Y., Xue, C., & Rivera, A. (2024). Innate cells and STAT1-dependent signals orchestrate vaccine-induced protection against invasive *Cryptococcus* infection. *mBio*, *15*(10), e01944-24. <https://doi.org/10.1128/mbio.01944-24>
- Wang, L., Wang, Y., Wang, F., Zhao, M., Gao, X., Chen, H., Li, N., Zhu, Q., Liu, L., Zhu, W., Liu, X., Chen, Y., Zhou, P., Lu, Y., Wang, K., Zhao, W., & Liang, W. (2022). Development and application of rapid clinical visualization molecular diagnostic technology for *Cryptococcus neoformans*/*C. gattii* based on recombinase polymerase amplification combined with a lateral flow strip. *Frontiers in Cellular and Infection Microbiology*, *11*, 803798. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcimb.2021.803798>
- Wang, Y., Pawar, S., Dutta, O., Wang, K., Rivera, A., & Xue, C. (2022). Macrophage mediated immunomodulation during *Cryptococcus* pulmonary infection. *Frontiers in Cellular and Infection Microbiology*, *12*, 859049. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcimb.2022.859049>
- Washington, E. J., Zhou, Y., Hsu, A. L., Petrovich, M., Tenor, J. L., Toffaletti, D. L., Perfect, J. R., & Brennan, R. G. (2024). Structures of trehalose-6-phosphate synthase, Tps1, from the fungal pathogen

Cryptococcus neoformans: A target for antifungals. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 121(32), e2314087121. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2314087121>

Wilder, J. A., Olson, G. K., Chang, Y. C., Kwon-Chung, K. J., & Lipscomb, M. F. (2002). Complementation of a capsule deficient *Cryptococcus neoformans* with CAP64 restores virulence in a murine lung infection. *American Journal of Respiratory Cell and Molecular Biology*, 26(3), 306–314. <https://doi.org/10.1165/ajrcmb.26.3.4479>

Yang, C., Huang, Y., Zhou, Y., Zang, X., Deng, H., Liu, Y., Zhang, Y., & Xue, X. (2022). *Cryptococcus* escapes host immunity: What do we know? *Frontiers in Cellular and Infection Microbiology*, 12, 1041036. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcimb.2022.1041036>

Yu, C. H., Sephton-Clark, P., Tenor, J. L., Toffaletti, D. L., Giamberardino, C., Haverkamp, M., Perfect, J. R., & Nielsen, K. (2021). Gene expression of diverse *Cryptococcus* isolates during infection of the human central nervous system. *mBio*, 12(6), e02313-21. <https://doi.org/10.1128/mBio.02313-21>

Zarrin, M., Jorfi, M., Amirrajab, N., & Rostami, M. (2010). Isolation of *Cryptococcus neoformans* from pigeon droppings in Ahwaz, Iran. *Turkish Journal of Medical Sciences*, 40(2), 313–316. <https://doi.org/10.3906/sag-0902-23>

Zhao, Y., Ye, L., Zhao, F., Zhang, L., Lu, Z., Chu, T., Wang, L., Zhang, L., Liu, Z., Sun, Y., Chen, M., Liao, W., Liao, G., Ding, C., Xu, Y., & Wang, L. (2023). *Cryptococcus neoformans*, a global threat to human health. *Infectious Diseases of Poverty*, 12(1), 18. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40249-023-01073-4>

